

Parkinson's Disease Priority Therapeutic Clinical Pipeline Report

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The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research

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Introduction

A critical measure of progress in delivering new treatments for those living with—or at increased risk for developing—Parkinson’s disease (PD) is the state and health of the therapeutic pipeline. A *healthy* pipeline should leverage the latest advances in therapeutic technology to target the diverse biology driving disease development as well as the unmet symptom management needs impacting daily life. Human testing (clinical trials) of these approaches should integrate sensitive and informative measures and endpoints of disease biology, progression and lived experience as well as efficient and inclusive study designs to speed clearer decisions on which therapies to move forward. Ensuring these ingredients are in place for maintaining a robust PD pipeline is core to the mission of The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson’s Research (MJFF).

This report tracks important therapies currently in *clinical development* for PD¹. It includes brief rationale and progress in key pipelines of therapeutic interest along with the development status of specific therapies. Where relevant, the report flags programs that have received financial or other significant enabling support from MJFF. While the report is extensive, it is not comprehensive of every intervention in development for PD. Rather, it represents treatments identified by MJFF as important given potential significance to the Parkinson’s community and for understanding MJFF role and impact.

The report primarily tracks *pharmacological* (i.e., small molecules) and *biological* (e.g., peptides, therapeutic antibodies and vaccines, gene therapy, cell therapy, etc.) treatments. We include a brief description of technology-enabled approaches (e.g., neuromodulation and other technological interventions) but highlight only areas reflecting MJFF funding focus. We do not include exercise, alternative therapies or behavioral interventions given challenges in tracking the many permutations these approaches take within the clinical testing pipeline. The report also primarily tracks therapies in development within the United States and Europe as these programs are generally easier to monitor and have more accessible information. Exceptions include trials in countries where study outcomes are expected to possibly inform or influence future consideration in the United States or Europe.

MJFF monitors numerous sources to assess the therapeutic pipeline, including online intelligence databases (e.g., Citeline, clinicaltrials.gov), company websites and our own engagement with industry sponsors². Information in this report is considered *non-confidential*, intended only as a guide for communicating progress and does not represent endorsement by MJFF of any specific therapy or company. We update and distribute this report on an annual basis, although we may generate supplements to the report as needed. Any errors or omissions are not intentional, and we welcome comments or suggestions to improve the accuracy and relevance of information in this report.

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¹ This report does not capture therapies in *preclinical development* although we may highlight such programs if a sponsor has publicly indicated plans to launch human testing within the next year.

² While we have used online AI-supported summaries to help research status of treatments, this report was written by staff of MJFF and not created through use of generative AI tools.

How MJFF Enables a Robust Parkinson’s Pipeline

Since the late 1990s, we have seen significant advances in understanding and treatment of PD pointing to new opportunities across the research and drug development effort.

Key progress includes:

- + *Exponential growth in our understanding of the biological basis of PD*, driven in large part by advances in deciphering genetic and cellular contributors to disease. Availability of tools to distinguish early biological signatures (e.g., the alpha-synuclein seeding amplification assay³) are driving conversations about the many forms PD may take and its relationship to other diseases with shared underlying pathology⁴.
- + *Approvals of new PD therapies* over the last decade that offer an increasing array of symptom-targeted options for people at early or more advanced stages of disease. While no approved treatment to date targets and modifies PD-associated pathology, many are currently in human testing. Additional approaches, fueled by waves of promising biological targets, are in preclinical stages of therapeutic exploration.
- + *Advances in tools to measure Parkinson’s biology*, as well as efforts to develop and refine methods to more sensitively assess patient-relevant clinical function. These newer measurement tools are enabling improved clinical trial designs and testing paradigms, ultimately leading to faster and more informative testing of promising therapies.
- + *Increased awareness of PD and its impact⁵* on those living with the disease and the communities in which they reside. This awareness is elevating advocacy to address policies and public priorities⁶ needed to support more robust research and improved healthcare.

Figure 1 | MJFF's Strategic Research Agenda for accelerating therapeutic development for PD

MJFF executes its mission through a multi-objective *strategic research agenda* built off this momentum in scientific progress. Key elements of our agenda (Figure 1) focus on advancing understanding of the biological basis of PD to inform more accurate diagnosis and prognosis, translating this insight into new precision medicine pipelines, addressing key barriers slowing clinical testing of promising therapies and catalyzing a community of stakeholders to deliver meaningful impact to those living with PD.

MJFF offers a range of programs and resources to support development of innovative treatments for people living with Parkinson’s disease (Figure 2).

³ See data validating SAA from the PPMI study in <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37059509/>

⁴ See two proposed biological frameworks in <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38267190/> and <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38267191/>

⁵ See the 2020 PD Economic impact study at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32665974/>

⁶ See the 2022 WHO report on PD at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35816299/>

Working with a global network of advisors and experts, including those living with PD, our strategies seek to address key financial and non-financial barriers researchers and drug makers face when moving an idea through the risky development process.

Figure 2 | How MJFF supports therapeutic development for PD

See our website for more information about the many ways MJFF is accelerating advances in PD

www.michaeljfox.org

The Drug Development Process

Moving an idea from disease understanding toward treatments for people is a multi-step process, with each step adding additional data and confidence that an approach is safe and offers meaningful benefit (Figure 3).

Figure 3 | Major phases of drug development

Types of Therapeutic Approaches

Advances in therapeutic technology offer many approaches for targeting disease processes and symptoms. Types relevant to the PD therapeutic pipeline include:

- + *Small Molecule Therapy*: small chemical compounds designed to interact with specific biological targets (often proteins) and alter their function in a beneficial way.
- + *Peptide Therapy*: a protein or protein fragment that can mimic the effects of or alter the function of other proteins.
- + *Antibody Therapy*: a kind of therapeutic immune protein that specifically binds cellular proteins and other targets (often those that may be challenging to selectively target with small molecules), delivered either directly (passive immunotherapy) or generated by the body through a vaccine (active immunotherapy).
- + *Gene Therapy*: an approach to deliver a therapeutic gene via a modified virus into cells which then use the delivered gene to instruct cells to produce a therapeutic protein of interest.
- + *RNA-Directed Therapies*: Small nucleotides (e.g., antisense oligonucleotides, small-interfering RNAs, etc.) that target and inhibit other RNA molecules to reduce or alter production of a specific protein.
- + *Cell/Tissue Therapy*: Transplanted or infused cells or tissues (often stem cell-derived) that may be used to replace damaged or lost cells (e.g., dopamine neurons) or that may support existing cells by secreting modulatory or other protective factors.
- + *Neuromodulation Therapy*: Approaches involving implanted or wearable stimulators or surgical lesioning to alter neural activity in the brain and reduce symptoms.
- + *Repurposed Therapy*: Therapies approved in one disease indication that are tested for possible benefits in another indication.

The Critical Role of Measurement Tools in the PD Pipeline

Human testing of new therapies requires an ability to measure the biological, clinical and patient-meaningful impact of a treatment. We can broadly classify these measurement tools in two ways:

- + *Biomarkers* that measure biological processes or biological responses to treatment. Examples of biomarkers can include measures of proteins or metabolites in body fluids such as in blood, urine or spinal fluid, as well as imaging scans and other tests that can detect pathology or altered physiology in the brain or body.
- + *Clinical Outcome Assessments* that measure how a person feels, functions or survives⁷. Examples include clinical scales that a doctor may use to describe a person’s symptom severity or questionnaires and diaries that a patient completes describing their experience with a disease. Emerging use of digital technologies is offering new ways to collect clinical outcome information.

In the context of a clinical trial testing a potential therapy, investigators can use these measurements to establish *endpoints* that define a change or other measure of disease state, progression or treatment effect. Selecting appropriate endpoints that reflect the relevant biological and/or clinical effect a trial seeks to demonstrate is one of the most essential (and challenging) aspects of rigorous clinical trial design.

Defining Measurement Tool Use in Drug Development

For biomarkers, the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and National Institutes of Health (NIH) established the Biomarkers, Endpoints, and other Tools (BEST) framework⁸ to help standardize definitions and intended use of biomarkers as measures of normal or pathological processes or responses to an intervention or exposure (Figure 4).

Biomarker contexts of use include:

- + *Risk biomarkers* that detect potential for developing disease in someone who does not currently have the disease (“Will I get the disease?”)
- + *Diagnostic biomarkers* that detect or confirm presence of disease (“Do I have the disease?”)
- + *Prognostic biomarkers* that predict likelihood of a particular disease event or clinical progression in someone with disease (“What might I expect from my disease?”)

⁷ See FDA description at <https://www.fda.gov/about-fda/clinical-outcome-assessment-coa-frequently-asked-questions>

⁸ For a detailed description of the BEST framework see <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5813875/>

- + *Pharmacodynamic response biomarkers* that measure whether a drug is engaging a therapeutic target or disease process (“How is the drug acting on relevant biology in my body?”)
- + *Predictive biomarkers* that suggest how someone may respond to a therapy (“Will a drug work for my particular disease?”)
- + *Monitoring biomarkers* that investigators can measure repeatedly to reflect overall response to a therapy (“How is the drug impacting my disease over time?”)
- + *Safety biomarkers* that measure potential signals of toxicity or other adverse events in response to a therapy (“Is the drug doing anything potentially harmful to me?”)

For clinical outcome assessments it is also important to define the concept of interest (i.e., what the assessment tool seeks to measure such as activities of daily living or motor function) and context of use (Figure 5). Careful consideration of these aspects is important for developing assessments that are fit for purpose in the context of a clinical trial.

Figure 5 | Developing patient-focused outcome measurement for clinical trials (from FDA guidance⁹)

Like biomarkers, there are several types of clinical outcome assessments:

- + *Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs)* that assess an individual’s status without interpretation by others often through self-reporting or interviews.
- + *Clinician-Reported Outcomes (ClinROs)* that come from a trained health care professional observing a patient.
- + *Observer-Reported Outcomes (ObsROs)* that come from someone other than the patient or health professional who may have more frequent (e.g., daily) interaction with the patient, such as a family member or close friend.

⁹ See FDA guidance at <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/patient-focused-drug-development-selecting-developing-or-modifying-fit-purpose-clinical-outcome>

- + *Performance Outcomes (PerfOs)* based on standard tasks performed by a patient and usually administered by a trained professional.

Measurement Tools in Use for Parkinson's Disease

To date, most Phase 2 and 3 clinical trials of treatments for PD use clinical outcome assessment tools to define primary endpoints of treatment effect¹⁰. A leading tool is the Movement Disorder Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UDPRS)¹¹. The scale includes both rater and patient (self)-administered components that assess a range of PD aspects and experiences. Parts I and II of the scale measure rater and patient-reported non-motor and motor aspects and experiences of PD, respectively, while Part III assesses motor signs through a clinical exam. Part IV covers important motor complications (dyskinesia and motor fluctuations). Given their focus (and regulatory interest) on patient and physician assessments of motor function and impact on daily activities, Parts II and III are often used by trial sponsors in the current PD pipeline to define key endpoints. However, recent discussions led by MJFF and other leaders in the PD community are highlighting opportunities for better refining the concepts of interest and contexts of use for clinical outcome assessments, especially as the field moves to an ability to diagnose disease earlier where newer assessment tools may be needed to detect more subtle signs of disease¹².

Biomarkers are emerging in use for PD clinical trials. Approved neuroimaging techniques to assess the dopamine system (e.g., DAT imaging) can ensure people exhibiting the symptoms of PD have impairments in the dopamine system that are considered a core feature of the disease. Testing for mutations in certain genes such as *LRRK2* and *GBA1* offers diagnostic, prognostic and predictive insight on people who may be more suitable for therapies targeting biology linked to these forms of PD. Additional biomarkers of specific biological processes may be used as supportive pharmacodynamic measures of treatment response. With the recent development of alpha-synuclein seeding amplification assays and regulatory acceptance for their use as biomarkers in clinical trials¹³, some drug makers are now starting to integrate this measure into therapeutic development plans.

MJFF and others continue to put much effort into identifying biomarkers for PD. These include development and validation of imaging methods to detect alpha-synuclein pathology in the brain as well as biomarkers (biochemical and imaging) of other potentially important disease biology such as inflammation, mitochondrial and endolysosomal function. With exciting advances in the use of alpha-synuclein seeding amplification assays, MJFF is also working closely with the research community to identify improved methods, including seeking alpha-synuclein measurement in blood or other tissues as well as to develop more quantitative methods of alpha-synuclein pathology detection. As these and other new biomarkers advance, we should ideally see their integration into PD clinical trials in the future.

¹⁰ Phase 1 trials mostly focus on safety and tolerability as their primary endpoints although may include additional clinical outcome assessments or biomarkers as secondary or exploratory measures

¹¹ See <https://www.movementdisorders.org/MDS/MDS-Rating-Scales/MDS-Unified-Parkinsons-Disease-Rating-Scale-MDS-UPDRS.htm>

¹² See <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11094181/>

¹³ See FDA letter of support at <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/biomarker-qualification-program/letter-support-los>

The Current Clinical Pipeline for PD

As of April 2025, we are monitoring the following number of unique treatments in active or soon-to-enter human testing (clinical development) for PD¹⁴.

178 TREATMENTS

More than just a number, these approaches target a range of biology and symptoms with strong potential for benefiting those with (and potentially at risk for) PD. An important way to understand this number is to examine it across important signals of promise (Figure 6). This allows us to check the overall health of the PD pipeline and in doing so, identify areas where MJFF support can address barriers and encourage greater progress.

Figure 6 | Key parameters useful for assessing overall health of the PD clinical pipeline.

The following sections of this report walk through these important parameters, providing a current snapshot of the PD clinical pipeline. Subsequent sections provide more deep-dive perspectives on specific treatments in clinical development for PD.

¹⁴ Includes treatments MJFF has identified as important and where a trial is active or has recently completed but remains in active development with commercial potential in US/EU. Programs testing the same therapy are counted once, unless they represent distinct new formulations. Includes programs expected to enter the clinic soon but excludes programs that have been publicly discontinued or technology-enabled devices and neuromodulation approaches. Changes in monitored treatment numbers from prior pipeline reports may reflect new entries, termination or removal of older programs and/or addition of programs missed in prior tracking and should not be used to make direct year-over-year trend comparisons.

Continued Momentum in New Therapy Approvals for PD

Since the first approvals of levodopa and other mostly dopamine-targeted therapies in the latter half of the 20th century, companies have delivered an ever-increasing array of new approaches (Figure 7). Many continue to focus on dopamine therapies to address core movement and mobility issues, especially at later disease stages. Some target other brain neurochemistry with the promise of managing PD non-motor symptoms and treatment complications¹⁵. Advances in surgical neuromodulation with deep brain stimulation or focused ultrasound ablation have added more options to target movement challenges. However, no treatment yet approved is known to slow or stop PD pathology and the resulting progressive disability it causes, and this remains a key focus of the current therapeutic development pipeline.

Figure 7 | Timeline of FDA Approvals for Important PD Treatments

¹⁵ For non-motor symptoms, physicians may use existing non-PD-specific therapies which are not reflected in our tracking of approved PD treatments. Whether to develop and market a PD-specific symptom therapy is a balance of understanding if there are unique PD biological aspects underlying the symptom as well as economics and other factors that may influence the ease of developing and getting market approval from regulators.

Recent new drug approvals continue to offer options although still focus on dopamine-directed therapy:

- + **Crexont** from **Amneal Pharmaceuticals** is a new extended and immediate-release combination pill of carbidopa and levodopa. Approved in Aug' 2024, it is intended to treat PD.
- + **Vylev** from **AbbVie** is a new combination of foscarbidopa and foslevodopa delivered through a 24-hour under-the-skin wearable infusion pump. Approved in Oct' 2024, it is intended to treat motor fluctuations in adults with advanced PD.
- + **Onapgo** from **Supernus Pharmaceuticals** is a new continuous under-the-skin infusion pump of the dopamine receptor-targeting therapy apomorphine. Approved in Feb' 2025, it is intended to treat motor fluctuations in adults with advanced PD.

A next wave of treatments nearing regulatory approval can also be seen in the specific pipeline sections later in this report.

Variety of Targeted Mechanisms Across Development Stages in the PD Pipeline

Treatments currently in human testing for PD target a range of biological pathways with potential for disease slowing or modulating brain chemistry to improve specific motor and non-motor symptoms (Figure 8)¹⁶. Pipelines in later human testing phases are dominated by attempts to optimize dopamine-directed therapy, but we also see a rising wave of novel approaches moving through early and mid-stage testing. Programs targeting key PD-linked biology such as alpha-synuclein, LRRK2 and GBA1 continue to expand with new players, while a large pipeline of approaches targeting immune and inflammatory processes has taken a leading position in large part due to the emergence of more targeted therapies (e.g., NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitors). Cell replacement efforts that leverage stem cell methods to generate new dopamine neurons for transplantation into the brain have also seen a large expansion in the clinical testing pipeline.

Reflected in this diverse biology is the emergence of precision medicine approaches with some treatments being targeted to specific populations of people with PD, such as those carrying genetic mutations in genes like GBA1 and LRRK2. As better biomarker tools emerge, more biology-driven selection of patients will become more frequent in PD clinical trials.

Figure 8 | Range of biological targets and pathways across the clinical development pipeline for PD.

¹⁶ For this report we use broad pathway designations based on stated or presumed treatment mechanisms of action. We may adjust designations in future reporting based on new information. Note that programs counted in this chart under certain pathways may be listed under different tables in this report based on putative mechanism of action. ‘Pending Launch’ = program we believe may enter clinical testing within the next year based on statements by sponsor or other trial information.

Majority of PD Clinical Pipeline Seeks Disease-Slowing

More than half of the active clinical pipeline for PD seeks to slow disease progression by targeting underlying disease pathology or providing general neuroprotective action (Figure 9)¹⁷. Other programs continue to focus on management of motor symptoms, especially in more advanced stages of PD. Approaches to improve non-motor symptoms are in development with particular emphasis on cognition and dementia.

Treatment Focus of the Current PD Clinical Pipeline

Figure 9 | Focus of treatments in the current clinical pipeline for PD

Increasing Innovation in Delivery Approaches in the PD Pipeline

Most therapeutic approaches in the PD pipeline leverage traditional small molecules (Figure 10), although recently these molecules are being delivered in new ways (e.g., via subcutaneous pumps vs. oral pills). We also see growing presence of cellular therapies (mostly cell replacement) as well as newer RNA-directed approaches for targeting and reducing protein levels of pathogenic proteins like alpha-synuclein (e.g., antisense oligonucleotides, RNA interference).

Types of Treatment Approaches in the PD Pipeline

Figure 10 | Delivery approaches in the current clinical pipeline for PD.

¹⁷ Intended use is based on presumed outcomes due to putative treatment mechanism or other indicators of program goal. Some treatments seek more than one intended use outcome (e.g., cognition and dementia plus motor impairment) and are counted twice for purposes of this visualization. Alpha-synuclein-targeting treatments seeking to slow progression in multiple system atrophy (MSA) are included given potential to similarly slow disease in PD.

A frequent approach reflected in the PD therapy pipeline today is that of *drug repurposing*: treatments used in one indication being tested (repurposed) for potential use in another indication such as PD (Box 1). While a compelling way to potentially speed testing of promising therapies that already have human safety and dosing understanding, repurposed drugs can still be challenging to test in a new disease¹⁸. Issues include differences in drug properties (e.g., ability to reach brain if the drug was not initially designed to do so), safety (e.g., whether drug was designed for chronic vs short-term use) or limited understanding of drug mechanism (e.g., disease-relevant biological target or other drug action not well defined). These questions hinder designing an informative clinical trial with appropriate drug-relevant biomarkers necessary for establishing clear evidence of benefit. Moreover, a lack of clear commercial and market paths (including payer reimbursement) for repurposed therapy can add to the complexity of future treatment access even if an approach shows potential promise. Importantly for people living with PD, repurposed therapies are often seen as faster ways to try potentially promising therapies since they may already be available on the market. However, like any new treatment, especially with limited definitive data in PD, people should carefully discuss these options with their doctors to understand safety or other risks.

*Box 1: Examples of Repurposed Drugs Under Consideration for PD**

Drug	Approved for	PD Potential
albuterol	asthma	aSyn reduction
alogliptin	diabetes	multiple hypothesized protective effects
allopregnanolone	postpartum depression	Multiple hypothesized protective effects
ambroxol	cough suppressant	GBA1 enhancer
atomoxetine	ADHD	gait & balance
azathioprine	immunosuppressant	anti-inflammation
bosutinib	leukemia	autophagy enhancer
carvedilol	heart failure	multiple hypothesized protective effects
ceftriaxone	antibiotic	cognition & dementia
citalopram	depression	cognition & dementia
doxycycline	antibiotic	aSyn reduction
fasudil	cerebral vasospasm	multiple hypothesized protective effects
GLP-1 receptor agonists: exenatide, liraglutide, lixisenatide, semaglutide	diabetes, obesity	multiple hypothesized protective effects
levetiracetam	epilepsy	Dyskinesia, psychosis, cognition & dementia
lithium	bipolar disorder	multiple hypothesized protective effects
metformin	diabetes	multiple hypothesized protective effects
montelukast	asthma, allergies	anti-inflammation
n-acetylcysteine	acetaminophen overdose	anti-oxidant
nilvadipine	hypertension	anti-inflammation
ondansetron	nausea & vomiting	psychosis
pyridostigmine	myasthenia gravis	constipation
sargramostim	immune stimulator	anti-inflammation
terazosin	prostatic hypoplasia, hypertension	improve energy production
ursodiol	gallstones	improve mitochondrial function
varenicline	smoking cessation	gait & balance

¹⁸ For a recent review of drug repurposing opportunities and challenges in neurodegenerative disorders see <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39971900/>

Robust Mix of Sponsors Advancing the PD Clinical Pipeline

A healthy PD pipeline should exhibit strong commercial interest in developing new therapies. Over 65% of active programs in human trials for PD are led by commercial sponsors, with academic and other non-commercial organizations leading the rest of the pipeline. Of these commercial programs, over half represent privately held startup and emerging biotechs suggesting a substantial presence of early-stage innovation. Publicly held biopharma companies, ranging from small to large, drive the remainder signaling strong investment from established players (Figure 11).

Figure 11 | Distribution of company types leading programs in the current PD pipeline. Startup and Emerging Biotech are private companies based on maturity, size and capital raised. Small, Mid- and Large Biopharma are public companies characterized by market capitalization.

Priority Parkinson’s Pipelines We Monitor

To successfully reach a world without PD requires developing diverse therapies targeting critical disease biology and symptoms (Figure 12). While not mutually exclusive in that some treatments have the potential for addressing both aspects of PD, this framing can clarify the primary intention of therapies in the pipeline and help better explain the main benefits such therapies may offer¹⁹. This is critical for educating the PD community so that doctors and patients understand the differences between treatments that may *improve* function by addressing symptoms vs those that may *preserve* function by targeting and slowing underlying disease biology and pathology.

Figure 12 | Types of treatments critical for addressing the needs of people living with and those at potential risk for PD.

For the purposes of this report, we have grouped specific treatment pipelines largely around their primary biological or (putative) pathological targets and pathways believed to contribute to PD. For drugs that target brain neurochemistry, which often include important symptom-addressing therapies (e.g., dopamine and other neurotransmitter-directed therapies), we have grouped these pipelines under their own section. For treatments that may be largely agnostic to specific disease pathology and thus may offer general neuroprotection, or that seek to replace cells lost in PD (e.g., with stem cell technologies), we have grouped these under separate pipeline sections as well. Finally, while not a formal or comprehensive tracking, we include a brief discussion of pipelines related to neuromodulation and other technology-assisted therapy. While not covered in the current report, growing interest in understanding the biological overlap between PD and other diseases with shared pathology (e.g., dementia with Lewy bodies) suggests opportunities to monitor and understand a broader set of therapeutic pipelines of potential interest in future reporting.

¹⁹ As the language around how these types of treatments are designated evolves, we may update how we categorize treatment pipelines in future versions of this report as needed. See our recent report on assessing cumulative meaningful benefits of disease-modifying therapies for synucleinopathies for examples of how such language is changing: https://www.rand.org/pubs/conf_proceedings/CFA3629-1.html

Alpha Synuclein-Directed Therapies

Therapeutic Rationale

Genetic and pathological evidence strongly links the alpha-synuclein (aSyn) protein to PD. Mutations in *SNCA*, the gene that instructs cells how to synthesize the aSyn protein, were the first genetic contributions researchers linked to PD. Shortly after, detection of aggregates of aSyn protein within so-called Lewy bodies in certain neurons of almost all people with PD—and later evidence that this pathology may spread from cell to cell—provided strong rationale that treatments targeting the production, spread and/or clearance of potentially toxic forms of the aSyn protein might be beneficial.

Current Landscape

Treatments in development targeting aSyn remain some of the most robust strategies in the current PD pipeline. Investigators are leveraging a variety of approaches, including use of therapeutic antibodies, vaccines and small molecules that specifically target and remove pathological forms of aSyn or seek to block its potential toxic effects. More recent therapies attempt to target the cell's protein production machinery and reduce aSyn protein levels using small molecules or RNA-directed therapies such as antisense oligonucleotides and RNA interference. Given similarities in the role aSyn pathology plays in PD and a related disorder called multiple system atrophy (MSA), many developers of aSyn-targeted therapies are exploring impact of their treatments in both diseases. As such, we monitor pipelines for both PD and MSA given the potential impact results in MSA may have on how similar therapies may work for PD.

Recent pipeline progress highlights:

- + **Roche** updated its Phase 2 study of alpha-synuclein-directed antibody therapy *prasinezumab* adding additional insight into the potential promise of this approach²⁰. While the therapy did not meet its primary goal of showing slowed motor progression overall, an analysis of a subgroup of participants who were on dopamine medication suggests a possible slowing effect. The company continues to assess the trial outcomes along with prior trial data to determine next steps.
- + **UCB** announced outcomes of its Phase 2 trial of alpha-synuclein inhibitor *minzasolmin*²¹. Unfortunately given limited reports of benefit, the company has terminated further development of the approach. The company's other antibody-based alpha-synuclein therapy **UCB-7853** remains in earlier clinical testing.
- + **Vaxxinity** and **AC Immune** each reported results of their testing of alpha-synuclein vaccines **UB-312**²² and **ACI-7104**²³, respectively, demonstrating safety and ability of these vaccines to generate alpha-synuclein-targeting antibodies.
- + **Bioarctic** finally returned to the clinic with its alpha-synuclein-directed antibody therapy *exidavnemab* (previously ABBV-0805) after AbbVie terminated its partnership in 2022. The Phase 2 trial will explore safety and a range of biomarkers in people with PD as well as a recently added cohort of people with MSA²⁴.

²⁰ See <https://www.roche.com/media/releases/med-cor-2024-12-19>

²¹ See <https://www.ucb.com/newsroom/press-releases/article/findings-from-minzasolmin-proof-of-concept-orchestra-study-shape-next-steps-in-ucb-parkinson-s-research-program>

²² See <https://ir.vaxxinity.com/news-releases/news-release-details/vaxxinity-ub-312-parkinsons-trial-results-published-nature>

²³ See <https://ir.acimmune.com/news-releases/news-release-details/ac-immune-reports-further-positive-interim-results-phase-2-trial>

²⁴ See <https://www.bioarctic.com/en/exidavnemab-phase-2a-study-expanded-to-include-msa-patients/>

- + **Annovis Bio** presented results from its Phase 3 trial of alpha-synuclein-lowering therapy **buntanetap** after several months of delay due to reported challenges in data analysis. The company pointed to positive signals in cognition and motor function, at least in some participants, but have yet to publish a full report²⁵.
- + **Eli Lilly** has launched a Phase 1 trial of its new RNA-directed alpha-synuclein-lowering agent **LY-3962681**²⁶.
- + **Lundbeck** launched a Phase 3 trial of aSyn-directed antibody therapy **amlenetug** in people with MSA²⁷. This represents one of the first immunotherapy approaches targeting aSyn to enter late-stage testing in an aSyn-related disease.
- + **Allyx Therapeutics** initiated a first-in-PD Phase 1 safety study for **ALX-001**, which targets a glutamate receptor in the brain the company believes may act as a neuronal binding site for aSyn pathology²⁸. The company is also pursuing the drug for Alzheimer’s disease based on a similar idea of blocking toxic effects of that disease’s key pathological amyloid protein.

MJFF Perspectives and Role

While strong rationale remains for targeting aSyn therapeutically, mixed results from some of the leading trials of aSyn-targeted therapy such as prasinezumab and minzasolmin point to continued need for understanding biological impact of these approaches. MJFF supports a range of efforts, including developing biomarkers and imaging methods for measuring aSyn, to inform and speed ongoing clinical development of these and future aSyn-directed therapy. As discussions evolve on use of biologically framed definitions of PD and related diseases linked to pathological forms of aSyn²⁹, future trials may provide a more precise test of whether and in whom such treatments may prove beneficial.

²⁵ See <https://www.annovisbio.com/press-release/annovis-bio-announces-new-data-from-phase-iii-parkinsons-study-highlighting-improvements-in-unified-parkinsons-disease-rating-scale-mds-updrs-and-cognition-after-treatment-with-buntanetap>

²⁶ See <https://lillyscience.lilly.com/download/63F5a8iEmt2Q1Xw6RDORF?directdownload=true>

²⁷ See <https://news.cision.com/h--lundbeck-a-s/r/lundbeck-initiates-a-phase-iii-trial-with-amlenetug-for-the-treatment-of-multiple-system-atrophy,c4071927>

²⁸ See <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2024/09/04/2940463/0/en/Allyx-Therapeutics-Announces-First-Parkinson-s-Disease-Patient-Treated-with-ALX-001.html>

²⁹ See <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38267190/>

Therapies Targeting Alpha-Synuclein

^a Treatments indicated with “Progression” are believed to slow disease presumably through targeting underlying pathology in PD or a sub-indication of PD (e.g., genetic form or related disease like MSA). Other listed indications generally imply treatments that seek to improve symptoms.

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^c Dates are estimated from publicly available press releases or intelligence platforms. Results are highlighted only if there is a public statement or publication and may not reflect results shared at conferences where abstract information is not publicly available. Recently discontinued programs are included but are not counted in active program tracking.

Active Programs

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
ABL-301	ABL Bio Sanofi	aSyn inhibitor	Antibody	Progression (PD)	1	-	Results pending 2025
UB-312	Vaxxinity	aSyn inhibitor	Vaccine	Progression (PD, MSA)	1	\$	PD: Phase 2 trial pending MSA: Pending update
UCB-7853	UCB	aSyn inhibitor	Antibody	Progression (PD)	1	-	<u>Phase 1 results reported</u>
BIIB-101 (ION-464)	Biogen Ionis	aSyn protein reduction	Antisense Oligonucleotide	Progression (MSA)	1	-	MSA: Results pending 2027- 2028
LY-3962681	Prevail Therapeutics Eli Lilly	aSyn protein reduction	siRNA	Progression (PD)	1	-	Results pending 2029
ALX-001	Allyx Therapeutics	mGluR5 silent allosteric modulator (putative aSyn toxicity inhibitor)	Small Molecule	Progression (PD)	1	\$, Other	Results pending 2025
ACI-7104	AC Immune	aSyn inhibitor	Vaccine	Progression (PD)	2	\$	<u>Interim results reported</u>
ATH-434	Alterity Therapeutics	aSyn inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression (MSA)	2	\$	<u>MSA: Phase 2 results reported</u>
Emrusolmin	MODAG Teva	aSyn inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression (PD, MSA)	2	\$	PD: Pending update MSA: Results pending 2027
Exidavnemab	Bioarctic	aSyn inhibitor	Antibody	Progression (PD, MSA)	2	-	<u>Phase 1 results reported</u> Phase 2 results pending 2026
MEDI-1341 (TAK-341)	AstraZeneca Takeda	aSyn inhibitor	Antibody	Progression (PD, MSA)	2	Other	PD: Pending update MSA: Results pending 2025

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Prasinezumab	Prothena Roche	aSyn inhibitor	Antibody	Progression (PD)	2	Other	Topline results reported
	University of Tübingen	aSyn inhibitor	Antibody	Progression (GBA1 PD)	2	\$	Pending trial start
Amlenetug	Lundbeck	aSyn inhibitor	Antibody	Progression (MSA)	3	-	MSA: Phase 2 results reported Phase 3 results pending 2029
Buntanetap	Annovis Bio	Amyloid protein reduction	Small Molecule	Progression (PD)	3	\$	Phase 3 results reported

Programs that may enter clinic soon

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Tridem Vaccine	Tridem Bioscience	aSyn pathology inhibitor	Vaccine	Progression (PD)	-	-	Trial pending 2025

Programs that have recently been discontinued

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Minzasolmin	Novartis UCB	aSyn pathology inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression (PD)	2	\$, Other	Phase 2 results reported Program discontinued

LRRK2-Directed Therapies

Therapeutic Rationale

Mutations in the gene leucine-rich repeat kinase 2 (LRRK2) may explain 1-40% of cases of PD depending on the ethnic population studied. LRRK2 is a kinase: a protein that chemically modifies other proteins to regulate cellular processes, such as the endolysosomal pathway, a system critical for transporting, recycling and degrading cellular components. Mutations linked to PD appear to increase this activity, which may impact how LRRK2 regulates other cellular pathways. Whether abnormal LRRK2 activity explains cases of PD in people without mutations is an area of active investigation.

Current Landscape

Programs in clinical testing seek to reduce LRRK2's pathological function primarily by inhibiting its kinase activity through small molecule inhibitors. Other approaches seek to reduce production of the LRRK2 protein itself by targeting its production with RNA-directed therapy or more recently using newer targeted protein degradation methods. To gain more insight into the broader potential of LRRK2-directed therapy, drug makers are testing for benefits of inhibiting LRRK2 in people both with and without genetic mutations.

Recent pipeline progress highlights:

- + **Arvinas** entered clinical testing in 2024 with its LRRK2-directed protein degrader **ARV-102** and recently presented top-line initial results showing safety and biomarker data supportive of continued development for PD³⁰.
- + **Brenig Therapeutics** entered Phase 1 human testing in 2024 with its LRRK2 inhibitor **BT-0267**³¹.
- + **Denali Therapeutics** launched a new Phase 2 study of LRRK2 inhibitor **DNL151 (BIIB122)** in 2024 specifically in people with PD who carry mutations in the LRRK2 gene³². Partner company **Biogen** continues to test the drug in a separate Phase 2 trial in both people with and without mutations in the LRRK2 gene.
- + **Neuron23** presented results of its Phase 1 trial of LRRK2 inhibitor **NEU-411** showing the drug safely targets the LRRK2 pathway and has now launched a Phase 2 trial³³.
- + **Ionis Pharmaceuticals** presented Phase 1 results of its RNA-directed antisense oligonucleotide approach **ION859 (BIIB-094)** for reducing LRRK2 protein levels showing the treatment to safely reduce levels of LRRK2 as well as other LRRK2-relevant biomarkers in people with or without LRRK2 genetic mutations³⁴. In early 2025, Biogen who had been testing the treatment stopped additional development leaving further testing of the approach uncertain³⁵.

³⁰ See <https://ir.arvinas.com/news-releases/news-release-details/arvinas-presents-first-human-data-investigational-oral-protac>

³¹ See <https://www.brenigther.com/publications/brenig-therapeutics-announces-the-initiation-of-first-in-human-clinical-trial-of-bt-267-a-best-in-class-lrrk2-inhibitor-for-parkinsons-disease>

³² See <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2024/12/05/2992284/0/en/Denali-Therapeutics-Announces-First-Participant-Dosed-in-Phase-2a-Study-of-LRRK2-Inhibitor-BIIB122-in-LRRK2-Associated-Parkinson-s-Disease.html>

³³ See <https://neuron23.com/neuron23-to-present-phase-1-healthy-volunteer-data-of-neu-411-a-brain-penetrant-lrrk2-inhibitor-at-ad-pd-2025/>

³⁴ See <https://www.aan.com/msa/Public/Events/AbstractDetails/61472>

³⁵ See <https://www.fiercebiotech.com/biotech/biogen-axes-asset-73b-buyout-plus-alzheimers-and-parkinsons-prospects>

MJFF Perspectives and Role

With strong genetic links to PD and compelling therapeutic rationale, MJFF has been a long-time and consistent supporter and funder of studies to translate LRRK2 research into treatments for people with PD. MJFF uses highly collaborative models³⁶ to support work around key challenges and barriers to progress (e.g., biomarkers, safety assessments, patient recruitment challenges) which have been instrumental in fueling the growing number of LRRK2 therapeutic programs in development.

³⁶ See our newest LRRK2 collaborative initiative: <https://www.michaeljfox.org/grant/lrrk2-investigative-therapeutics-exchange-lite>

Therapies Targeting LRRK2

^a Treatments indicated with “Progression” are believed to slow disease presumably through targeting underlying pathology in PD or a sub-indication of PD (e.g., genetic form or related disease like MSA). Other listed indications generally imply treatments that seek to improve symptoms.

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Active Programs

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
FB-418	1 st Biotherapeutics	c-Abl kinase inhibitor, LRRK2 kinase inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	1	Other	Results pending 2025
BT-0267	Brenig Therapeutics	LRRK2 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	1	Other	Results pending 2025
S-221237	Oncodesign Servier	LRRK2 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	1	-	Results pending 2025 Oncodesign to develop further
ARV-102	Arvinas	LRRK2 protein degrader	Small Molecule	Progression	1	Other	Phase 1 results reported
ION-859 (BIIB-094)	Ionis	LRRK2 reduction	RNA-Directed Therapy Antisense Oligonucleotide	Progression (LRRK2 and Idiopathic PD)	1	\$, Other	Phase 1 results reported
DNL-151 (BIIB-122)	Denali Biogen	LRRK2 kinase inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression (LRRK2 and Idiopathic PD)	2	Other	Results pending 2026
	Denali			Progression (LRRK2 PD)	2	Other	Results pending 2028
NEU-411	Neuron23	LRRK2 kinase inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression (“LRRK2-Driven PD”)	2	Other	Phase 1 results reported Phase 2 results pending 2027

Programs that may enter clinic soon

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
SRT-055	Seal Rock Therapeutics	LRRK2/ASK1 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	-	-	Trial pending 2025

GBA1-Directed Therapies

Therapeutic Rationale

Certain variants in the *GBA1* gene increase risk for PD. GBA1 codes for the protein glucocerebrosidase (“GCase”) which regulates metabolism of important lipids in cells and is an important component of the endolysosomal system, a system critical for degrading and recycling cellular components. Dysfunction in GCase activity may lead to toxic accumulation of certain lipids or other potentially cell-damaging effects. PD patients with *GBA1*-associated gene mutations may have an earlier age of disease onset, can exhibit more cognitive issues and may progress more rapidly than other forms of PD, although this may be mutation specific. Whether altered GCase activity explains PD cases without *GBA1* mutations is an area of active study. Recent genetic discoveries in non-European populations, including people of African descent, indicate that *GBA1* may be associated with larger numbers of PD cases in some populations³⁷.

Current Landscape

Drug makers currently and primarily seek to enhance GCase activity with the goal of reducing potentially toxic accumulated lipids. Approaches include small molecule drugs to increase GCase activity use gene therapy to deliver functional copies of the *GBA1* gene.

Recent pipeline progress highlights:

- + **Vanqua Bio** announced initial results of its Phase 1 testing of GBA1-directed therapy **VQ-101** showing ability to significantly and safely enhance glucosylceramidase activity³⁸.
- + **Gain Therapeutics** reported initial Phase 1 data showing that its GBA1-directed therapy **GT-02287** could safely enhance glucosylceramidase activity in healthy individuals and has now moved to testing in people with PD, including people with and without mutations in the *GBA1* gene³⁹.
- + Researchers at **Lawson Research Institute** presented results from a Phase 2 trial of the putative GBA1-directed repurposed therapy **ambroxol** in people with PD dementia. While the drug appeared safe and able to elevate GBA1-associated GCase activity, the researchers did not see meaningful impact on the primary dementia measures tested. Full publication of the results is still pending.

MJFF Perspectives and Role

GBA1 gene mutations contribute to some of the most common genetic forms of PD and represent an important therapeutic area of focus. MJFF supports work to identify factors that may influence GCase protein function and its impact on cellular pathways such as the endolysosomal pathway which may point to additional therapeutic targets and ways of identifying people at risk for this form of PD.

³⁷ See publication at <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37633302/>

³⁸ See <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2025/03/27/3050414/0/en/Vanqua-Bio-to-Present-at-the-AD-PD-2025-International-Conference.html>

³⁹ See <https://gaintherapeutics.com/newsroom/press-releases/press-releases-2025/gain-therapeutics-doses-first-participant-in-phase-1b-clinical-trial-of-gt-02287-in-parkinsons-disease/>

Therapies targeting GBA1

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Active Programs

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
GT-02287	Gain Therapeutics	GCase enhancer	Small Molecule	Progression (GBA1 PD and Idiopathic PD)	1	\$	Phase 1 results reported
VQ-101	Vanqua Bio	GCase enhancer	Small Molecule	Progression (GBA1 PD and Idiopathic PD)	1	\$	Interim results reported Full results pending 2025
BIA 28-6156 (LTI-291)	Bial	GCase enhancer	Small Molecule	Progression (GBA1 PD)	2	\$, Other	Results pending 2026
PR-001	Prevail Therapeutics Eli Lilly	GCase expression enhancer	Gene Therapy	Progression (GBA1 PD)	2	Other	Results pending 2029
Ambroxol	Agyany Pharmaceuticals	Mucolytic agent (Putative GCase enhancer)	Small Molecule	Progression (GBA1 PD)	2	-	Results pending 2025
	IRCCS National Neurological Institute			Progression (GBA1 PD)	2	-	Results pending 2025
	Lawson Health Research Institute			Progression (PD Dementia)	2	-	Phase 2 topline results reported
	University College London			Progression (GBA1 PD and Idiopathic PD)	3	-	Results pending 2029
	University Medical Center Groningen			Progression (GBA1 PD)	3	-	Results pending 2025

Programs that may enter clinic soon

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
CAP-003	Capsida Biotherapeutics	GCase expression enhancer	Gene Therapy	Progression	-	-	Trial pending 2025
GBA Gene Therapy	Voyager Therapeutics	GCase expression enhancer	Gene Therapy	Progression	-	-	Trial pending 2025

Therapies Targeting Immune System Function and Dysfunction

Therapeutic Rationale

Given its interaction with aging and environment, researchers have long explored the immune system as a possible contributor to neurodegenerative disorders such as PD. The immune system works through two arms.

- + An *innate* immune arm provides a fast, non-specific response to an immunological threat. This response may include physical barriers (e.g., skin and other tissue membranes) or more complex physiological and biological responses. Inflammation is an important component of the innate immune response whereby the body uses various factors to attract immune cells to a site of infection to target a foreign pathogen or damaged cell, often through processes such as phagocytosis where specialized immune cells engulf and digest foreign material.
- + An *adaptive* immune arm involves a more specialized response whereby certain immune cells (e.g., T and B cells) coordinate to specifically identify and target a pathogen. Working together, these cells support generation of antibodies that move through the body to identify the specific pathogen and neutralize it. Given the multi-step signaling necessary for adaptive immune responses, these often work on a more prolonged timescale than innate responses. The adaptive immune system can also develop immune memory for pathogens, such that an exposure can be more quickly identified and targeted in the future. (This is why once exposed to a virus we develop future immunity from that virus.)

While researchers initially thought the brain was largely protected (*privileged*) from the immune system, in truth there is a more complex relationship. Some immune cells may access the brain, and the brain also has its own resident cells (e.g., microglia) that act in similar ways as cells in the body to target sites of injury or damage in the brain. Genetic and pathological evidence point to potential roles of immune factors in development and progression of PD and this remains a long-standing research effort.

Current Landscape

A robust number of therapies targeting various aspects of the immune system is increasingly evident in the PD pipeline. While the approaches range with respect to targeting innate vs adaptive immune arms, one frequent focus has been to target inflammation through the inhibition of the so-called inflammasome, primarily through one of its key protein complexes NLRP3. Given the central role the inflammasome plays in initiating inflammatory responses, drug makers are excited about developing and testing approaches to target this mechanism for PD.

Recent pipeline progress highlights:

- + Several programs advanced NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitors into Phase 2 human testing including **Ventyx Biosciences**⁴⁰ with **VTX-3232** and **Ventus Therapeutics**⁴¹ with **VENT-02**.
- + **Longevity Biotech** began human testing of its immunomodulating therapy **LBT-3627** in healthy individuals and people with PD⁴².

⁴⁰ See <https://ir.ventyxbio.com/news-releases/news-release-details/ventyx-biosciences-announces-initiation-dosing-phase-2a-trial>

⁴¹ See <https://www.ventustx.com/ventus-therapeutics-announces-first-patient-dosed-in-phase-2a-clinical-trial-evaluating-vent-02-an-oral-brain-penetrant-nlrp3-inhibitor-in-parkinsons-disease/>

⁴² See <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06466525>

- + **BioVie** has launched a new Phase 2 trial to continue testing its anti-inflammatory and insulin-sensitizing therapy **bezisterim** in people with PD⁴³.
- + **TrueBinding** launched a Phase 2 study of its anti-inflammation-focused anti-galectin-3 antibody **TB006** in people with PD⁴⁴.
- + **IntelGenx** launched a PD Phase 2 trial of **montelukast**, a drug approved for asthma and seasonal allergies which the company is now repurposing for possible disease-slowing benefits in both AD and PD⁴⁵.
- + **Biohaven** reported good Phase 1 safety and target engagement of its TYK2/JAK1 inhibitor **BHV-8000**, and has initiated Phase 2 development for PD⁴⁶.

MJFF Perspectives and Role

A key challenge in effective development of therapies targeting the immune system for PD is that it is still not clear which aspects are most relevant to underlying disease pathogenesis. This is important for being able to identify people with PD who are most likely to respond to anti-inflammatory or immunomodulatory therapy. A lack of sensitive tools and biomarkers for assessing the immune system and brain inflammation processes in people has hindered the field and is an area of particular focus for MJFF support.

⁴³ See <https://investors.bioviepharma.com/news/news-details/2025/BioVie-Initiates-SUNRISE-PD-Clinical-Trial-Assessing-Bezisterim-in-Early-Parkinsons-Disease-with-First-Patient-Enrolled/default.aspx>

⁴⁴ See <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06773962>

⁴⁵ See <https://www.intelgenx.com/newsrooms/newsrooms1/134-2024-news/1011-ntelennouncesfirstarkinsonsiseaseatientso20240408>

⁴⁶ See <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/biohaven-reports-recent-business-developments-and-fourth-quarter-and-full-year-2024-financial-results-302389517.html> ; <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/biohaven-enrolls-first-patient-into-phase-2-trial-in-early-parkinsons-disease-targeting-neuroinflammation-with-novel-brain-penetrant-tyk2jak1-inhibitor-302467788.html>

Therapies Targeting Immune System Function and Dysfunction

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Active Programs

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
PDM608	The Scripps Research Institute	GM-CSF	Biologic	Progression	1	\$, Other	Results pending 2025
Sargramostim	Partner Therapeutics	GM-CSF	Biologic	Progression	1	-	Results pending 2025
Dapansutrile	Olatec Therapeutics University of Cambridge	NLRP3 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	1	\$	Phase 2 trial pending
Selnoflast	Roche	NLRP3 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	1	Other	Results pending 2025
AAD-2004 (Crisdesalazine)	GNT Pharma	Prostaglandin inhibitor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment, Progression	1	-	Phase 2 trial pending 2025
EC-5026	EicOsis	Soluble epoxide hydrolase inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	1	\$	Results pending 2027
A-005	Alumis	TK2 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	1	-	Phase 1 results reported
LBT-3627	Longevity Biotech	VPAC2 agonist	Peptide	Progression	1	\$, Other	Results pending 2025
PXS-4728A	Syntara Pharmaxis	AOC3 and MAO-B inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression (iRBD)	2	-	Results pending 2025
Bezisterim	BioVie	ERK1/2 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment, Progression	2	-	Ongoing trial
TB-006	TrueBinding	Galectin antagonist	Antibody	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2026
Azathioprine	University of Cambridge	Immuno-suppressant	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2025
NT-0796	NodThera	NLRP3 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Next trial pending

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
INT-0043 (Montelukast)	IntelGenx	Leukotriene antagonist	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2027
Montelukast	Stockholm Health Care Services	Leukotriene antagonist	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Pending update
Usnoflast	Zydu Lifesciences	NLRP3 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Ongoing trial
VENT-02	Ventus Therapeutics	NLRP3 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	<i>Phase 1 results reported</i> Phase 2 results pending 2025-2026
VTX-3232	Ventyx Biosciences	NLRP3 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2025
BHV-8000	Biohaven	JK1/TK2 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	3	Other	Phase 3 results pending 2027

Programs that may enter clinic soon

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
SNK-01	NKGen Biotech	Autologous NK cells	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Progression	-	-	Trial pending 2025
AVI-009	Avicenna Biosciences	ROCK1/ ROCK2 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia	-	-	Trial pending 2025

Therapies Targeting Other Disease Biology

Therapeutic Rationale

Increased understanding of biological processes disrupted in PD—including data from genetic studies⁴⁷—points to a host of molecular targets and pathways that could offer hope for slowing disease. In addition to the immune system (see earlier separate pipeline overview section), cellular mechanisms linked to mitochondrial and metabolic impairment, microbiome and processes involved in handling and degrading misfolded proteins all represent promising avenues for therapeutic development.

Current Landscape

A robust pipeline of drugs targeting various hypothesized mechanisms contributing to PD and its progression are in active clinical testing.

Recent pipeline progress highlights:

- + Data from trials testing GLP-1 receptor agonists continue to paint a complex picture of possible benefits for PD. D&D Pharmatech subsidiary **Neuraly** published full results of its Phase 2 testing of **NLY01** (a pegylated form of exenatide) in people showing a lack of benefit on PD motor or non-motor features. Investigators in France (**LIXIPARK Study Group**) also published data from its repurposed testing of **lixisenatide** suggesting possible slowing of movement decline in people with PD. However, published data from a Phase 3 trial of **exenatide** led by investigators at **University College London** showed lack of benefit over a 96-week period⁴⁸. **Kariya Pharmaceuticals** launched a Phase 1 trial of dual GLP-1/GIP receptor agonist **KP405** in healthy individuals and people with PD, offering a potentially different approach to targeting this pathway⁴⁹.
- + Trials of therapies targeting c-Abl have also struggled with both **Inhibikase** who is testing the c-Abl inhibitor **risvodetinib**⁵⁰ and **Sun Pharma Advanced Research Company** who is testing c-Abl inhibitor **vodobatinib**⁵¹ suspending further development after results from their respective Phase 2 trials showed limited benefits in people with PD. However, new company **ABLi Therapeutics** has indicated it will continue development of **risvodetinib** with plans for a Phase 3 trial⁵².
- + **Mission Therapeutics** began testing its mitophagy-enhancing USP30 inhibitor **MTX-325** in healthy individuals and people with PD⁵³
- + Researchers at the **University of Ghent** in Belgium published results from a Phase 2 trial of **fecal microbiota transplantation** suggesting that the approach may offer mild benefits in PD motor function⁵⁴.

⁴⁷ See the latest PD GWAS preprint at <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2025.03.14.24319455v1>

⁴⁸ See <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39919773/>

⁴⁹ See <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06189170>

⁵⁰ See <https://www.fiercebiotech.com/biotech/inhibikase-therapeutics-hits-pause-parkinsons-program-it-prioritises-lung-drug>

⁵¹ See <https://www.financialexpress.com/business/healthcare-sun-pharma-halts-trial-of-its-parkinsons-disease-drug-as-it-fails-to-show-treatment-benefits-3452475/>

⁵² See <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2025/05/21/3085719/0/en/ABLi-Therapeutics-Announces-Details-of-the-End-of-Phase-2-Meeting-with-FDA-for-Evaluation-of-Risvodetinib-as-a-Treatment-for-Parkinson-s-Disease.html>

⁵³ See <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/mission-therapeutics-commences-landmark-trial-of-mtx325-a-potential-disease-modifying-treatment-for-parkinsons-disease-302094843.html>

⁵⁴ See <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38686220/>

- + **Glaxo** began testing its PON2-directed anti-oxidative stress therapy **vutiglabin** in a Phase 2 trial in people with PD⁵⁵.

MJFF Perspectives and Role

Given the complex nature of PD, no single treatment may be sufficient to address all possible underlying biology linked to the disease. Therefore, maintaining a diverse range of approaches in clinical testing is critical. MJFF supports work to expand biological understanding of PD including partnering with initiatives like the *Aligning Science Across Parkinson's Collaborative Research Network* and *Global Parkinson's Genetics Program*⁵⁶. Insight from these and other programs such as MJFF's *Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative*⁵⁷ and *Targets to Therapies Initiative*⁵⁸ point to additional targets that may be translated into future therapies. Efforts are also underway to leverage so-called platform trials that allow sponsors to test multiple potentially disease-slowing therapies in parallel for PD⁵⁹. Such trial platforms may offer greater efficiency and cost-effectiveness although can also be logistically and methodologically challenging to perform. To date, only one platform effort (the *Australian Parkinson's Mission*⁶⁰) is actively testing therapies but newer platforms are nearing launch including *The Edmond J. Safra Accelerating Clinical Trials in Parkinson's initiative*⁶¹ and MJFF's *Path to Prevention platform trial*⁶².

⁵⁵ See <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06329141>

⁵⁶ See more about Aligning Science Across Parkinson's programs at <https://parkinsonsroadmap.org/>

⁵⁷ See more at <https://www.ppmi-info.org/>

⁵⁸ See more about how MJFF is advancing novel target translation at <https://www.michaeljfox.org/grant/targets-therapies-initiative>

⁵⁹ See recent perspective on emerging platform trials for PD at <https://movementdisorders.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/mds.29899>

⁶⁰ See more at <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11931937/>

⁶¹ See <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36856727/>

⁶² See <https://www.ppmi-info.org/study-design/path-to-prevention-platform-trial>

Therapies Targeting Other Disease Biology

^a Treatments indicated with “Progression” are believed to slow disease presumably through targeting underlying pathology in PD or a sub-indication of PD (e.g., genetic form or related disease like MSA). Other listed indications generally imply treatments that seek to improve symptoms.

^b \$ = MJFF provided direct funding to program at some point in its development; Other = MJFF provided other significant enabling support (e.g., recruitment or trial protocol advice). MJFF continuously engages with companies to understand challenges and opportunities which may not be fully reflected in this table.

^c Dates are estimated from publicly available press releases or intelligence platforms. Results are highlighted only if there is a public statement or publication and may not reflect results shared at conferences where abstract information is not publicly available. Recently discontinued programs are included but are not counted in active program tracking.

Active Programs

Mitochondrial & Metabolic Stress

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Ursodiol	Sheffield Teaching Hospital	Mitochondrial enhancer	Small Molecule	Progression	1	\$	Pending update
ABBV-1088	AbbVie	PINK1 activator	Small Molecule	Progression	1	-	Results pending 2025
MTX-325	Mission Therapeutics	USP30 inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	1	\$, Other	<i>Interim results reported</i> Full results pending
KP-405	Kariya Pharmaceuticals	GLP-1/GIP agonist	Peptide	Progression	1	-	Ongoing trial
HBI-002	Hillhurst Biopharmaceuticals	Hypoxic preconditioning	Small Molecule	Progression	1	\$, Other	Phase 2 trial pending 2025
Terazosin	Cedars-Sinai Medical Center	PGK1 activator (Putative metabolic enhancer)	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2026
Terazosin	University of Iowa	PGK1 activator (Putative metabolic enhancer)	Small Molecule	Progression	2	\$	Pending update
Carvedilol	Cedars-Sinai Medical Center	Adrenergic receptor blocker (Putative metabolic enhancer)	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2025
Metformin	Tanta University	HGP inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2025
Vutiglabin	Glaxo	PON2 modulator	Small Molecule	Progression	2	\$	Results pending 2026
N-Acetylcysteine	Thomas Jefferson University	ROS inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2025
Exenatide	Stockholm Health Care Services	GLP-1 Receptor Agonist	Peptide	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2027

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Lixisenatide	University Hospital, Toulouse Sanofi	GLP-1 Receptor Agonist	Peptide	Progression	2	-	Pending update
NLY-01 (Pegylated Exenatide)	Neuraly	GLP-1 Receptor Agonist	Peptide	Progression	2	-	Pending update
Semaglutide	Japan Agency for Medical Research and Development	GLP-1 Receptor Agonist	Peptide	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2026
Hypoxia Therapy	Radboud University	Hypoxic preconditioning	Other	Progression	2	\$, Other	Phase 2 results reported
Novolin R (Intranasal Insulin)	HealthPartners Institute	Insulin receptor agonist	Peptide	Motor Impairment, Cognition & Dementia	2	-	Phase 2 results reported
ISN-GSH (Insulin-glutathione)	Gateway Institute	Insulin receptor agonist + reducing agent	Peptide	Cognition & Dementia	2	-	Phase 2 results pending 2025
Exenatide	University College London	GLP-1 Receptor Agonist	Peptide	Progression	3	\$	Phase 3 results reported

Autophagy

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Bosutinib	Neurological Associates of West Los Angeles	Tyrosine kinase inhibitor	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	1	-	Results pending 2026
Radotinib	Il-Yang Pharmaceutical	c-Abl kinase inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2027
Risvodetinib	Inhibikase	c-Abl kinase inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	\$, Other	Phase 2 interim results reported Further development may continue with new company ABLi Therapeutics
KM-819	FASciate Therapeutics (Kainos Medicine)	FAF1 antagonist	Small Molecule	Progression	2	Other	Results pending 2025

Microbiome

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Fecal Bacteriotherapy (PRIM-DJ2727)	University of Texas	Fecal microbiota transplants	Biologic	Motor Impairment	1	-	Pending update
Fecal Bacteriotherapy	Medical University of Warsaw	Fecal microbiota transplants	Biologic	Motor Impairment, Progression	2	-	Results pending 2025

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Fecal Bacteriotherapy	Metagen Therapeutics	Fecal microbiota transplants	Biologic	Motor Impairment	2	-	Results pending 2027
Fecal Bacteriotherapy	Leiden University Medical Center	Fecal microbiota transplants	Biologic	Motor Impairment	2	-	Ongoing trial
Fecal Bacteriotherapy	University Ghent	Fecal microbiota transplants	Biologic	Motor impairment	2	-	<i>Phase 2 trial results reported</i>
Rifaximin	University of California, San Francisco	Antibiotic	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	-	Results pending 2025

Multi-Therapy Platform Trials

These treatments are being tested in parallel using a platform trial approach and are bundled here for clarity. For purposes of our tracking, each drug is categorized by their putative mechanism of action for addressing PD.

Platform Sponsor	Therapeutic	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Stage	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Australian Parkinson's Mission ⁶³	Albuterol	Adrenoreceptor agonist (Putative aSyn expression reducer)	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Trial Ongoing
	Nilvadipine	Calcium channel blocker (Putative anti-inflammatory)					
	Alogliptin	DPP-4 inhibitor (GLP-1 elevator)					
	Ambroxol	Mucolytic agent (Putative GCase enhancer)	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Trial Ongoing
	Doxycycline	Antibiotic (Putative aSyn inhibitor)					
	Ambroxol + Doxycycline	Combination Therapy					

Programs that may enter clinic soon

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
2'-Fucosyl-D-lactose (OM002)	Intrinsic Medicine	Microbiome modulator	Small Molecule	Constipation, Cognition & Dementia, Motor impairment	-	-	Trial launch pending 2025
ASHA-091	Asha Therapeutics	Dynamin 1 like inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	-	-	Trial pending 2025

⁶³ See further details at <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11931937/>

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
NRG-5051	NRG Therapeutics	mPTP inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression		\$	Trial pending 2025

Programs that have recently been discontinued

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Vodobatinib	SPARC	c-Abl kinase inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	Other	<u>Phase 2 results reported</u> PD deprioritized.

Therapies Seeking General Neuroprotection

Therapeutic Rationale

The goal of many therapeutic approaches for diseases like PD is to target pathological mechanisms believed to trigger or contribute to degeneration. However, another approach is to target biology that may help existing brain cells resist and possibly recover from the toxic effects of pathology. An exact distinction between such neuroprotective approaches and those focused on modifying disease biology is fuzzy, but one example is the identification of growth factors and other cellular factors that help to sustain and maintain healthy brain cells. These approaches may be generally agnostic to disease cause making them potentially beneficial to all people with PD.

Current Landscape

Prior attempts to deliver growth factors into the brains of people with PD have not been generally successful. Newer approaches using improved methods and advanced technologies are underway. Additional factors that may offer protective benefits to brain cells are also under development, including approaches that leverage cell therapy based on the idea that infused cells may produce potentially neuroprotective molecules.

Recent pipeline progress highlights:

- + Bayer subsidiary **AskBio** launched a Phase 2 trial of GDNF gene therapy **AB-1005** after seeing good safety from a prior Phase 1 study⁶⁴.
- + **Herantis** launched a new Phase 1 trial of CDNF-mimicking drug **HER-096** to include testing in people with PD⁶⁵.
- + **Athira Pharma** seems to have terminated further testing of its hepatocyte growth factor therapy **fosgonimeton** for PD, possibly due to less-than-positive results from a previous AD trial along with other company needs for finding strategic alternatives⁶⁶.
- + **NurrOn Pharmaceuticals** and its partners HanAll Biopharma and Daewoong Pharmaceutical reported completion of a Phase 1 study of its Nurr1-directed therapy **ATH-399A**, indicating a good safety profile for the approach and a desire to continue further development⁶⁷.
- + **InnoMedica Schweiz** launched plans for a Phase 2 trial of **talineurin (TLN-1)** a liposomal formulation of the potentially protective ganglioside GM1, for possible disease-slowing benefits in PD⁶⁸.

MJFF Perspectives and Role

While slowing or stopping underlying disease biology is a primary goal of PD therapeutic development, there is strong rationale and potential for targeting mechanisms that may help existing brain cells withstand these pathological processes. However, for many of these approaches it can be challenging to interpret if and how they may be working and whether potential effects seen reflect true neuroprotection. One area of difficulty is in

⁶⁴ See <https://www.bayer.com/media/en-us/askbio-initiates-recruitment-to-its-phase-2-parkinsons-disease-trial/>

⁶⁵ See <https://herantis.com/news-events/releases/?publicationId=18d79e47-a5f6-4958-be78-0641449abfcd>

⁶⁶ See <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2024/11/07/2977129/0/en/Athira-Pharma-Reports-Third-Quarter-2024-Financial-Results-and-Pipeline-and-Business-Updates.html>

⁶⁷ See <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/hanall-biopharma-daewoong-pharmaceutical-and-nurron-pharmaceuticals-announce-successful-completion-of-a-first-in-human-study-for-potential-disease-modifying-therapy-for-parkinsons-disease-302315158.html>

⁶⁸ See <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06431971>

the use of cell-based therapies, such as those derived from mesenchymal stem cells (e.g., from bone marrow or other tissues of the body) given the complex biological ways they may act. A laxer regulatory approach to these cell-based approaches in many countries also means that some clinics can sell cell-based therapies directly to people often with limited information on what is being delivered or data on long-term safety and benefits. As of today, no cell-based therapy has been approved for PD and people seeking out such treatments should speak with their doctors and carefully weigh the potential risks.

Therapies Seeking General Neuroprotection

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^b \$ = MJFF provided direct funding to program at some point in its development; Other = MJFF provided other significant enabling support (e.g., recruitment or trial protocol advice). MJFF continuously engages with companies to understand challenges and opportunities which may not be fully reflected in this table.

^c Dates are estimated from publicly available press releases or intelligence platforms. Results are highlighted only if there is a public statement or publication and may not reflect results shared at conferences where abstract information is not publicly available. Recently discontinued programs are included but are not counted in active program tracking.

Active Programs

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
NX-210c	Axoltis Pharma	Beta 1 integrin agonist	Peptide	Progression	1	-	Ongoing trial
HER-096 (xCDNF)	Herantis	CDNF agonist	Small Molecule	Progression	1	\$	Phase 2 trial pending 2026
Allo-pregnanolone	University of Arizona	GABA receptor allosteric modulator (putative neuroprotectant)	Small Molecule	Progression	1	-	Results pending 2025
MT-101-5	Mthera Pharma	Multiple putative protective mechanisms	Other	Progression	1	-	Phase 2 trial launch pending
Stem Cell Therapy	Shanghai iCELL Biotechnology	Human amniotic epithelial stem cells	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Progression	1	-	Results pending 2026
Talineuren (GM1)	InnoMedica	Neural regeneration	Biologic	Progression	1	-	Phase 1 results pending 2025 Phase 2 trial launch pending
ATH-399A (HL-192)	Daewoong Pharmaceutical HanAll Biopharma NurrOn Pharmaceuticals	Nurr1 agonist	Small Molecule	Progression	1	\$, Other	<i>Phase 1 results reported</i>
NNI-362	Neuronascent	p70S6 kinase phosphorylation stimulator	Small Molecule	Progression	1	-	Phase 2 trial pending
IRX-4204	Io Therapeutics	RXR agonist	Small Molecule	Progression	1	\$	Phase 2 trial pending
MSCTC-0010	IMAC Holdings	Umbilical cord-derived mesenchymal stem cells	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	1	-	Ongoing trial
HB-adMSC	Hope Biosciences	Adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2026
Allogeneic MSCs	University of Texas	Bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cell	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Progression	2	\$	Ongoing trial

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
AAV2-GDNF	Asklepios Bio (Bayer)	GDNF Expression Enhancer	Gene Therapy	Progression	2	Other	Phase 1 results published Phase 2 results pending 2028
Fosgonimeton	Athira Pharma	HGF agonist	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	2	\$, Other	Pending strategic review
Lithium	University at Buffalo	Putative Nurr1 agonist	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2026
NTCell	Algorae Pharmaceuticals	Pig choroid plexus cells	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Progression	2	-	Pending update
Fasudil	Technical University of Munich	ROCK inhibitor	Small Molecule	Progression	2	-	Results pending 2025

Programs that may enter clinic soon

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Peripheral Nerve Tissue Transplants	University of Kentucky	Sural Nerve Tissue Transplantation (autologous)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Cognition & Dementia	-	-	Trial launch pending 2025
CHMA-1004	Chemestmed	Gene expression inhibitor/ RNA	Gene Therapy	Progression	-	-	Trial pending 2025
OT-003	Pangea Bio	TrkB tyrosine kinase stimulant	Small Molecule	Progression	-	-	Trial pending 2025

Therapies Targeting Brain Neurochemistry

Therapeutic Rationale

People with PD experience a range of symptoms, including hallmark motor symptoms like slow movement, limb rigidity and rest tremor, as well as other movement problems (e.g., gait and balance) and so-called ‘non-motor’ symptoms (e.g., cognitive impairment, dementia, psychiatric challenges, mood disorders, sleep issues and constipation). The symptoms of PD are largely an expression of altered brain signaling due to the dysfunction and/or degeneration of certain cells in the brain. The most well-known example for PD is loss of neurons in the substantia nigra region of the brain that produce the neurotransmitter dopamine and the subsequent impact this has on movement control. This discovery led to the use of levodopa and other dopamine-targeted therapies as frontline therapeutic options for PD given their ability to increase production or signaling of dopamine in the brain. Understanding of the pathology and altered brain signaling underlying many non-motor symptoms is less advanced and while there are a few therapeutic options targeting other neurotransmitters (e.g., serotonin, norepinephrine, acetylcholine), this remains an active area of investigation.

Current Landscape

The pipeline of therapies targeting various neurochemical systems in the brain is vast and moves rapidly, making it challenging to track. Dopamine-directed therapies have revolutionized the ability to restore core movement issues in people with PD. However, as the disease progresses a long-standing focus of the therapeutic pipeline has been to optimize treatments to address complications that arise as PD advances. These complications include dyskinesias (abnormal movements that can arise over time when using some dopamine medications) and motor fluctuations (e.g., sudden OFF periods when treatment seems to stop working). Additionally, non-motor symptoms are often treated with existing symptom-targeted medicines, but some drug makers are exploring PD-specific approaches or at least attempting to gather more rigorous data on treatment responses in people with PD.

Recent pipeline progress highlights:

- + It has been an active time for regulatory approvals of additional dopamine-directed therapies for PD. **AbbVie** received FDA approval for **Vyalev**, its under-the-skin pump-delivered formulation of foslevodopa/foscarbidopa for the treatment of motor fluctuations in adults with advanced PD⁶⁹. **Amneal Pharmaceuticals** received approval for **Crexont**, an optimized reformulation of levodopa/carbidopa for the treatment of PD⁷⁰. **Supernus Pharmaceuticals** received FDA approval for **Onapgo**, its under-the-skin apomorphine infusion device⁷¹. **Mitsubishi Tanabe Pharma** has filed a response to FDA for approval of under-the-skin levodopa product **ND0612** with an expected decision date by end of the year⁷².
- + Several groups are testing new approaches for delivering dopamine. **PureIMS** reported data showing its **Levodopa Cyclops** inhaled levodopa product had comparable safety and pharmacokinetics to marketed

⁶⁹ See <https://news.abbvie.com/2024-10-17-U-S-FDA-Approves-VYALEV-TM-foscarbidopa-and-foslevodopa-for-Adults-Living-with-Advanced-Parkinsons-Disease>

⁷⁰ See <https://investors.amneal.com/news/press-releases/press-release-details/2024/Amneal-Receives-U.S.-FDA-Approval-for-IPX203-for-Treatment-of-Parkinsons-Disease-to-Be-Launched-as-CREXONT-Carbidopa-and-Levodopa-Extended-Release-Capsules/default.aspx>

⁷¹ See <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2025/02/04/3020423/19871/en/Supernus-Announces-FDA-Approval-of-ONAPGO-apomorphine-hydrochloride-for-Parkinson-s-Disease.html>

⁷² See <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/mitsubishi-tanabe-pharma-america-announces-us-fda-acceptance-of-new-drug-application-resubmission-for-investigational-nd0612-for-the-treatment-of-motor-fluctuations-in-parkinsons-disease-302466198.html>

product Inbrija, setting it up for possible faster regulatory consideration⁷³. **SNLD** presented results from a small Phase 2 study of an intranasal delivery formulation of levodopa **TR-012001** showing ability to quickly increase blood levodopa levels and improve motor function in some participants⁷⁴. **InBrain Pharma** and collaborators at Lille University published results of a Phase 2 study of an aerobic dopamine (**A-Dopamine**), a pump-delivered approach to infuse non-oxidized dopamine directly into the brain, showing the approach to significantly reduce OFF time⁷⁵.

- + A next wave of potentially optimized dopamine agonists is coming. Pipeline leader **AbbVie** reported positive motor benefit outcomes from three Phase 3 trials of its new once-daily dopamine agonist **tavapadon**, positioning the company well to seek regulatory approval soon⁷⁶. **Pharma Two B** updated on positive motor benefits of its dopamine-targeted combination therapy of pramipexole and rasagiline (**P2B001**) indicating plans to apply to regulators⁷⁷. **Kissei Pharmaceutical** launched a Phase 2 study of its dopamine receptor agonist **matsupexole (KDT-3594)**⁷⁸.
- + **IRLAB Therapeutics** is progressing multiple programs through human testing. Published data from its Phase 2 study of dopamine receptor antagonist **mesdopetam** showed that while the therapy did not increase participant ON time, it did appear to have anti-dyskinetic effects and a Phase 3 study is now planned to further confirm these effects⁷⁹. The company has also reported data from its Phase 2 testing of serotonin and adrenaline-targeting **pirepemat** demonstrating ability of the treatment to reduce fall rates in some trial participants with PD⁸⁰. A third program with drug **IRL757** is focused on addressing apathy and is expected to move into testing in people with PD based on good safety data in healthy individuals⁸¹.
- + **Cerevance** offered further data on its GPR6-targeted therapy **solengepras (CVN424)**, indicating that in a Phase 2 trial as a monotherapy in early, untreated people with PD, the drug had limited benefit⁸². The company is continuing testing of the drug in a Phase 3 trial in people already on dopamine therapy given prior Phase 2 data suggesting potential of CVN424 as an adjunct therapy⁸³.
- + Several programs reported mixed results and progress on possible dyskinesia-targeted therapies. Bukwang Pharmaceuticals subsidiary **Contera Pharma** reported limited ability of its serotonin-targeting combination of buspirone and zolmitriptan (**JM-010**) to reduce dyskinesia in a Phase 2 trial and has halted further development of the approach⁸⁴. (The company's new levodopa/carbidopa formulation **CP-012** is still in early human testing.) Similar negative findings were reported by a research group from **Assistance Publique-Hôpitaux de Paris** showing little added benefit of **buspirone** to reduce dyskinesias

⁷³ See <https://pureims.com/international-congress-of-parkinsons-disease-and-movement-disorders-poster-on-levodopa-cyclops/>

⁷⁴ See <https://www.neurology.org/doi/10.1212/WNL.00000000000210464>

⁷⁵ See <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41591-024-03428-2>

⁷⁶ See <https://parkinsonsnewstoday.com/news/aan-2025-tavapadon-offers-rapid-sustained-motor-benefits/>

⁷⁷ See <https://parkinsonsnewstoday.com/news/p2b001-valuable-first-line-treatment-early-parkinsons/>

⁷⁸ See <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06722729>

⁷⁹ See <https://parkinsonsnewstoday.com/news/phase-3-trial-mesdopeta-parkinsons-dyskinesia-planned/>

⁸⁰ See https://irlab.se/mfn_news/irlab-publishes-interim-report-for-the-period-january-march-2025/

⁸¹

See <https://www.accessnewswire.com/newsroom/en/healthcare-and-pharmaceutical/irlab-reports-positive-results-from-the-second-part-of-a-phase-i-stud-1032605>

⁸² See <https://www.cerevance.com/media/cerevance-presents-topline-results-from-phase-2-ascend-trial-of-solengepras-as-monotherapy-treatment-for-early-stage-parkinsons-disease-at-ad-pd-2025>

⁸³ See <https://www.cerevance.com/media/cerevance-doses-first-patient-in-pivotal-phase-3-arise-trial-of-solengepras-for-treatment-of-parkinsons-disease>

⁸⁴ See <https://www.koreabiomed.com/news/articleView.html?idxno=24113>

in a Phase 3 study⁸⁵. More positively, *Celon Pharma* shared top-line Phase 2 results of its PDE10A inhibitor *CPL500036* showing reductions in levodopa-induced dyskinesia⁸⁶. Finally, *Neurolix* published results from Phase 2 testing of its serotonin-targeting drug *befiradol (NLX-112)* demonstrating apparent reduction in levodopa-induced dyskinesia and improved motor function⁸⁷.

- + *MeiraGTx* reported outcomes of early testing of their *AAV-GAD gene therapy* approach seeking to boost brain GABA levels and modulate neural activity in people with PD. Results support safety as well as potential initial efficacy of the gene therapy to reduce motor symptoms⁸⁸.
- + Several groups seek to improve cognitive impairment in people with PD. *CuraSen* reported Phase 2 data from tests of its combination therapy of *CST-2032* (a beta2 adrenoceptor agonist) and *CST-107* (nadolol used to block non-brain effects of CST-2032) suggesting possible effects on cognition in people with AD and PD⁸⁹. *Sage Therapeutics* reported data from Phase 2 testing of its glutamate-targeting drug *dalzanemdor (SAGE-718)* showing lack of benefit in people with PD exhibiting mild cognitive impairment⁹⁰. *Anavex* submitted an applicant to European regulators for approval of *blarcamesine* for Alzheimer’s disease⁹¹ based on reported positive late-stage testing data. The company has previously reported potential benefits in people with PD dementia⁹² although more clinical testing would be needed before seeking similar regulatory consideration for PD.
- + Researchers at the *University of California San Francisco* reported potential benefits of the psychedelic drug *psilocybin* on a range of motor and non-motor symptoms in a small open-label trial⁹³ and are now continuing to explore the approach in a larger controlled Phase 2 study for depression in PD⁹⁴.

MJFF Perspectives and Role

Addressing and acutely reducing the impact of PD symptoms is critical to making PD more manageable and increasing quality of life. MJFF supports a range of efforts, including therapeutic development and testing of potential symptom-targeted therapies as well as establishing clarity on patient-meaningful functional measurements. More recently, MJFF is putting greater focus on addressing gait disturbances (i.e., balance and freezing issues linked to falls), sleep issues as well as cognitive impairment and dementia.

⁸⁵ See <https://www.mdabstracts.org/abstract/multicentric-randomized-control-trial-of-buspirone-in-levodopa-induced-dyskinesias/>

⁸⁶ See <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2025/03/04/3036951/0/en/Strong-Proof-of-Concept-Data-from-Phase-2-Trial-of-PDE10A-Inhibitor-CPL-36-a-Novel-Once-Daily-Treatment-of-Levodopa-Induced-Dyskinesia-in-Parkinson-s-Disease.html>

⁸⁷ See <https://www.neurolix.com/en/news/232-18-march-2025-neurolix-publishes-positive-phase-2a-trial-results-for-nlx-112-in-parkinson-s-disease.html>

⁸⁸ See <https://investors.meiraqtx.com/news-releases/news-release-details/meiraqtx-announces-positive-data-randomized-sham-controlled>

⁸⁹ See <https://www.curasen.com/curasen-therapeutics-announces-oral-presentation-of-additional-positive-phase-2a-data-with-cst-2032-cst-107-in-patients-with-alzheimers-or-parkinsons-disease-at-ad-pd-2024-i/>

⁹⁰ See <https://investor.sagerx.com/news-releases/news-release-details/sage-therapeutics-announces-topline-results-phase-2-precident>

⁹¹ See <https://www.anavex.com/post/anavex-life-sciences-announces-submission-of-blarcamesine-maa-for-treatment-of-alzheimer-s-disease-t>

⁹² See <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2023/03/30/2637477/29248/en/ANAVEX-2-73-Blarcamesine-Shows-Clinical-Benefit-in-Long-Term-48-Week-Phase-2-Extension-Study-in-Patients-with-Parkinson-s-Disease-Dementia.html>

⁹³ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41386-025-02097-0>

⁹⁴ See <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06455293>

Therapies Targeting Dopamine

^a Treatments indicated with “Progression” are believed to slow disease presumably through targeting underlying pathology in PD or a sub-indication of PD (e.g., genetic form or related disease like MSA). Other listed indications generally imply treatments that seek to improve symptoms.

^b § = MJFF provided direct funding to program at some point in its development; Other = MJFF provided other significant enabling support (e.g., recruitment or trial protocol advice). MJFF continuously engages with companies to understand challenges and opportunities which may not be fully reflected in this table.

^c Dates are estimated from publicly available press releases or intelligence platforms. Results are highlighted only if there is a public statement or publication and may not reflect results shared at conferences where abstract information is not publicly available. Recently discontinued programs are included but are not counted in active program tracking.

Active Programs

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Infudopa (LD/CD)	Dizlin Medical Design	Dopamine precursor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	1	-	Pending next trial
CP-012	Contera Pharma (Bukwang) BDD Pharma	Dopamine receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	1	-	Ongoing trial
Lu-AF28996	Lundbeck	Dopamine receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	1	-	Results pending 2026
MLR-1019 (Armesocarb)	Adhera Therapeutics	Dopamine reuptake inhibitor	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia	1	-	Pending update
TRN-501	SNLD	Dopamine precursor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	1	-	Results pending 2025
HNC-364	Guangzhou Henovcom Bioscience	MAO-B inhibitor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	1	-	Results pending 2025
DopaFuse (LD/CD)	SynAgile	Dopamine precursor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	-	Pending update
PIMS-703 (Levodopa)	PureIMS	Dopamine precursor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	-	Pending update
A-Dopamine	University Hospital, Lille InBrain Pharma	Dopamine receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	-	<i>Phase 2 results reported</i> Phase 3 trial pending
AZ-009 (Apomorphine)	Alexza Pharmaceuticals	Dopamine receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	Other	Pending update
KDT-3594	Kissei Pharma	Dopamine receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	-	Ongoing trial
CTC-413 (Pramipexole)	Chase Therapeutics	Dopamine receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	-	Results pending 2026
Mesdopetam	IRLAB Therapeutics	Dopamine receptor antagonist	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia	2	-	Phase 3 trial pending

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Glovadalen	UCB	Dopamine receptor positive allosteric modulator	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	Other	Results pending 2025
TR-012001 (Intranasal Levodopa)	SNLD	Dopamine precursor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	-	Phase 2 results reported
P2B-001 (Prampexole + Rasagiline)	Pharma Two B	Dopamine agonist + MAO-B inhibitor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	3	-	Pending update
Apomorphine	Rennes University Hospital	Dopamine receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	3	-	Results pending 2025
CVN-424	Cerevance	Dopamine signaling modulator	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	3	Other	Results pending 2026
Tavapadon	Abbvie	Dopamine receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	3	Other	Phase 3 topline results reported NDA pending 2025
ND-0612 (LD/CD Pump)	Neuroderm (MT Pharma)	Dopamine precursor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	Reg	\$, Other	FDA decision pending 2025

Programs that may enter clinic soon

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Lecigon (LD/CD/Ent Pump)	Intrance Medical Systems	Dopamine precursor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	-	-	Phase 3 trial pending
SER-252 (POZ-apomorphine)	Serina Therapeutics	Dopamine receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	-	-	Trial pending 2025
SB-0110	Sinopia Biosciences	Dopamine pathway modulator	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia, Motor Impairment	-	\$	Trial pending 2025

Therapies Targeting Other Brain Neurochemistry

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Active Programs

Glutamate

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
AV-101	VistaGen	AMPA receptor agonist, NMDA antagonist	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia	1	-	Pending update
Ceftriaxone	BrainX Corporation	Cell wall synthesis inhibitor	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	2	-	Results pending 2025
DAAOI-P	China Medical University Hospital	DAO inhibitor NMDA receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	2	-	Results pending 2025
Ketamine	VA Office of Research and Development	NMDA receptor antagonist	Small Molecule	Depression	2	-	Phase 2 trial launch pending 2025
Ketamine	Yale University	NMDA receptor antagonist	Small Molecule	Depression	2	\$, Other	<u>Phase 2 interim results reported</u> Phase 2 results pending 2025
PT-001 (Ketamine)	Pharmather	NMDA receptor antagonist	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia	2	-	Phase 3 trial pending
Memantine + AChE Inhibitor	Cumbria Northumberland Tyne and Wear NHS Foundation Trust University of Melbourne	NMDA receptor antagonist	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	3	-	Results pending 2027

Acetylcholine

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Blarcamesine	Anavex Life Sciences	Sigma-1 receptor agonist, ACh receptor antagonist	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia, Progression	2	\$, Other	Phase 3 trial pending
Donepezil	Inje University	AChE inhibitor	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	2	-	<u>Phase 2 results reported</u>
Pyridostigmine	University of Vermont	AChE inhibitor	Small Molecule	Constipation	2	-	Results pending 2025
Varenicline	University of Michigan	ACh receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Gait & Balance	2	\$	Phase 2 trial launch pending 2025

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Rivastigmine	NHS University of Bristol	AChE inhibitor	Small Molecule	Gait & Balance	3	-	Results pending 2025

Epinephrine & Norepinephrine

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Atomoxetine	Radboud University	Adrenergic uptake inhibitor	Small Molecule	Gait & Balance	2	\$, Other	Results pending 2027
Pirepemat	IRLAB Therapeutics	Adrenoreceptor antagonist, Serotonin receptor antagonist	Small Molecule	Gait & Balance	2	-	Phase 2 results reported
Methylphenidate	Ralph H. Johnson VA Medical Center	Norepinephrine & dopamine dual reuptake inhibitor	Small Molecule	Apathy	2	-	Phase 2 trial launch pending

Serotonin

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
NH-130	Jiangsu Nhwa Pharmaceutical	Serotonin receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Psychosis	1	-	Phase 1 results reported
Befiradol	Neurolix	Serotonin receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia	2	\$, Other	Pending Update
JM-010	Bukwang Pharmaceutical	Serotonin receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia	2	Other	Phase 2 topline results reported
Ondansetron	University College, London	Serotonin receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Psychosis	2	-	Results pending 2027
Psilocybin	UCSF Silo Pharma	Serotonin receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Anxiety, Depression	2	\$	Phase 2 results reported
Pimavanserin (Nuplazid)	University Hospital of Strasbourg	Serotonin receptor antagonist	Small Molecule	Impulse Control Disorder	2	-	Results pending 2025
Citalopram	University of Michigan	Serotonin reuptake inhibitor (potential amyloid inhibitor)	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	2	-	Results pending 2026
Buspirone	Assistance Publique - Hôpitaux de Paris	Serotonin receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia	3	-	Phase 1 results reported

Other Neurochemical Targets

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
IRL-757	IRLAB Therapeutics	Cortical enhancer (undisclosed mechanism)	Small Molecule	Apathy	1	\$, Other	Phase 1 topline results reported Phase 1 trial in PD pending 2025

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	The Fourth Affiliated Hospital of Zhejiang University School of Medicine	Nucleotide reverse transcriptase inhibitor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	1	-	Results pending 2026
PRAX-944	Praxis Precision Medicines	Calcium channel antagonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	1	Other	Next trial pending
DGX-001	Viage Therapeutics	Vagal nerve stimulator	Peptide	Cognition & Dementia	1	-	Phase 2 trial pending
Cannabidiol	Parkinson's UK King's College London	Cannabinoid receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Psychosis	2	-	Results pending 2026
Cannabidiol	University of Colorado	Cannabinoid receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	-	Pending update
Cannabidiol	Laboratorio Elea Phoenix S.A.	Cannabinoid receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	-	Results pending 2026
AAV-GAD	MeiraGTx	GABA expression enhancer	Gene Therapy	Motor Impairment	2	\$, Other	Phase 2 results reported Phase 3 trial pending 2025
Istradefylline	Kyowa Kirin	Adenosine receptor antagonist	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	2	-	Results pending 2025
Lenrispodun	Intra-Cellular Therapies	PDE inhibitor	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	\$, Other	Results pending 2025
CPL-36	Celon Pharma	PDE inhibitor	Small Molecule	Dyskinesia	2	-	Phase 2 topline results reported
AGB-101 (Levetiracetam)	AgeneBio	SV2A modulator	Small Molecule	Psychosis	2	-	Results pending 2026-2027
Levetiracetam	University of Queensland	SV2A modulator	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	2	-	Results pending 2026
JZP-385	Jazz Pharma	Calcium channel antagonist	Small Molecule	Motor Impairment	2	Other	Topline results pending 2025
Zonisamide	Sumitomo Pharma	Calcium channel antagonist	Small Molecule	Sleep	3	-	Phase 3 results reported
Crisugabalin	Haisco Pharmaceutical Group	Calcium channel antagonist	Small Molecule	Pain	3	-	Results pending 2027

Programs that have recently been discontinued

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
SAGE-718	Sage Therapeutics	NMDA receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	2	Other	<u>Phase 2 topline results reported.</u> Program discontinued
TAK-071	Takeda	ACh receptor agonist	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia, Gait & Balance	2	\$, Other	Program discontinued
Irsenontrine (E-2027)	Eisai	PDE inhibitor	Small Molecule	Cognition & Dementia	2	-	Program discontinued

Therapies Seeking Cell Replacement

Therapeutic Rationale

Given the importance of dopamine neuron loss as a key driver of movement symptoms in people with PD, the concept of possibly replacing these cells surgically through cell or tissue transplantation has long been of interest. Initial efforts using dopamine-producing tissues provided some early proof-of-concept that such an approach might offer improvements in movement in some people. However, the surgical methods, initial side effects (e.g., transplant-associated dyskinesias) and barriers to sourcing quality tissues containing dopamine cells made these approaches challenging to scale. The isolation of human embryonic stem cells (hESCs) in the late 1990s and subsequent advances in generation of so-called induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) in the early 2000s led to an explosion of research to develop methods for generating replacement cells for neurodegenerative disorders like PD.

There are two general approaches for delivering a stem cell-based transplant to patients:

- + *Allogeneic* transplantation uses cells obtained from a donor who is not the patient, much like what is done in some forms of cancer or donated organ transplants. Such an approach allows for a small number of donated stem cell lines to be used for a larger number of recipients. However, transplantation usually requires additional immunosuppression treatments to ensure the transplanted cells are not rejected by the patient.
- + *Autologous* transplantation uses cells obtained from the same patient who will receive the transplant. With the discovery and refinement of iPSC techniques, which allow researchers to generate stem cells from other cells such as skin or blood, there is potential for offering tailored, patient-specific stem cell transplants that do not require immunosuppression. However, given additional costs and manufacturing, this approach comes with its own unique challenges.

Stem cells can be obtained from a variety of sources although currently most therapeutic efforts leverage either hESC or iPSC sources⁹⁵

Current Landscape

While researchers have been generating dopamine-producing cells from stem cells in the lab for many years, developing methods that can be scaled and ultimately used safely in people has been a major challenge. Today, as the approaches have been refined and have passed regulatory hurdles for manufacturing and safety, there is an ever-increasing number of groups, both academic and commercial, bringing stem cell-based dopamine cell transplantation into human testing for PD. In the current pipeline we see both allogeneic and autologous methods under investigation as well as hESC and iPSC cell sources, but whether one approach will offer better outcomes or ease-of-use is not yet clear and will require more data.

Recent pipeline progress highlights:

- + Several leading groups have reported early clinical trial results from their stem cell transplantation programs. Bayer subsidiary *BlueRock Therapeutics*, who is developing *bemdaneprocel* (a human

⁹⁵ For a patient-friendly description of stem cells and stem cell-based treatments, see the International Society for Stem Cell Research guide to stem cell treatments at https://www.isscr.org/s/ISSCR_PatientHandbook_v12_Feb2024_Redesign_v4b.pdf

embryonic stem cell-based transplantation approach), and investigators at *Kyoto University*, who are testing an *induced pluripotent stem cell-derived dopamine transplantation* method, each published results of early human testing⁹⁶. Both groups found their transplants to be safe, to survive over the course of the trial period and to induce possible movement benefits in PD participants. BlueRock has already indicated plans to move quickly to a Phase 3 trial⁹⁷. *Sumitomo Pharma*, who has collaborated closely with the research group in Kyoto, has initiated a new sponsored study in the U.S. with its allogeneic iPSC approach *DSP-1083*⁹⁸.

- + Other groups also reported progress of ongoing dopamine cell replacement approaches, including *S.Biomedics (TED-A9)*⁹⁹, *Aspen Neuroscience (ANPD001)*¹⁰⁰, *iRegene Therapeutics (NN-001, NN003)*¹⁰¹, *Shanghai UniXell Biotechnology (UX-DA001)*¹⁰² and several academic-led programs from *Massachusetts General Hospital* and *McLean Hospital*¹⁰³.

MJFF Perspectives and Role

While treatments targeting disease pathology offer potential for slowing progression and onset of disability and new symptoms, they may not necessarily improve symptoms. This can be particularly challenging in those with more advanced disease. Dopamine-directed and other symptom management approaches can acutely improve function but a strong desire to try to replace damaged neurons has fueled a robust and growing therapeutic pipeline for PD around use of stem cell transplantation approaches. MJFF was an early supporter of much foundational work in the use of stem cell-derived dopamine cell replacement. With newer programs entering the clinic, MJFF is closely monitoring progress and opportunistically supporting activities that may inform this promising pipeline.

⁹⁶ See <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-025-08845-y> and <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-025-08700-0>

⁹⁷ See <https://www.bayer.com/media/en-us/bluerock-therapeutics-advances-investigational-cell-therapy-bemdaneprocel-for-treating-parkinsons-disease-to-registrational-phase-iii-clinical-trial/>

⁹⁸ See <https://www.sumitomo-pharma.com/news/20240328.html>

⁹⁹ See <https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20241126606645/en/S.BIOMEDICS-Investigational-Cell-Therapy-for-Parkinsons-Disease-With-TED-A9-Shows-Positive-Data-at-12-months-in-Phase-12a-Clinical-Trial>

¹⁰⁰ See <https://aspenneuroscience.com/aspenneuroscience-announces-6-month-aspiro-phase-1-2a-clinical-trial-results-of-personalized-cell-therapy-for-parkinsons-disease/>

¹⁰¹ See <https://parkinsonsnewstoday.com/news/fda-oks-parkinsons-clinical-trial-nouvneu001-cell-therapy/>

¹⁰² See <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06778265>

¹⁰³ See <https://www.mcleanhospital.org/news/clinical-trial-tests-novel-stem-cell-treatment-parkinsons-disease>

Therapies Seeking Cell Replacement

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Active Programs

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
iNSC-DAP Cells	Xuanwu Hospital, Beijing	Dopamine cell replacement (autologous iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	1	-	Results pending 2027
UX-DA001	Shanghai UniXell Biotechnology Co.	Dopamine cell replacement (autologous iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	1	-	Results pending 2028
Bemdaneprocel	BlueRock Therapeutics	Dopamine cell replacement (allogeneic ESC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	1	\$	Phase 3 trial pending 2025 based on FDA feedback
STEM-PD	Region Skåne Lund University Novo Nordisk University of Cambridge	Dopamine cell replacement (allogeneic ESC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	1	-	Results pending 2027-2028
ISC-hpNSC	International Stem Cell Corporation	Dopamine cell replacement (allogeneic iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	1	-	Ongoing trial
iPSC-DA Cells	Massachusetts General Hospital	Dopamine cell replacement (autologous iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	1	-	Results pending 2029
iPSC-DA Cells	McLean Hospital	Dopamine cell replacement (autologous iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	1	\$	Results pending 2028
NN-003	iRegene Therapeutics	Dopamine cell replacement (allogeneic iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	1	-	Ongoing trial
TED-A9	S. Biomedics	Dopamine cell replacement (allogeneic ESC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	2	-	<i>Phase 2 interim results reported</i> Full results pending 2026
ANPD-001	Aspen Neuro	Dopamine cell replacement (autologous iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	2	-	<i>Phase 2 interim results reported</i> Results pending 2030
iPSC-DA Transplants	Kyoto University Sumitomo Pharma	Dopamine cell replacement (allogeneic iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	2	\$	Results pending 2028
NN-001	iRegene Therapeutics	Dopamine cell replacement (allogeneic iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	2	-	Results pending 2029

Programs that may enter clinic soon

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
ICA-07	iCamuno Biotherapeutics	Dopamine cell replacement (autologous iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	-	-	Trial launch pending 2025
RNDP-001	Kenai Therapeutics	Dopamine cell replacement (allogeneic iPSC)	Cell/Tissue Therapy	Motor Impairment	-	\$	Trial pending 2025

Therapeutic Neuromodulation and Other Technology-Enabled Interventions

Therapeutic Rationale

Medications targeting dopamine systems in the brain remain a leading approach for addressing movement and mobility challenges in PD. However, these therapies become less effective over time or are associated with increasingly disabling complications, such as dyskinesia and motor fluctuations (e.g., sudden OFF periods). Moreover, non-motor symptoms can become increasingly disabling over time and while some medications can help, these remain significant unmet needs for people living with PD. An alternative to medication is to directly target abnormal brain activity or to leverage assistive technologies and approaches that can help people better navigate and manage their symptoms.

Current Landscape

Approved surgical interventions for neuromodulation include *deep brain stimulation* (DBS) and *focused ultrasound* (FUS) ablation therapy. Both seek to alter abnormal brain activity underlying core movement issues in PD and may be an option for some patients.

- + DBS works by surgically implanting electrodes to stimulate specific brain regions. By adjusting this stimulation, a trained clinician can help people improve motor function.
- + FUS ablation therapy may also improve function by lesioning (with focused sound waves) a small part of the brain circuitry impacted by PD.

DBS and FUS continue to be optimized in ways to improve possible benefits to people with PD. Advances have included exploring use in earlier stages of the disease, creating ‘smarter’ DBS that can dynamically respond to someone’s clinical state, assessing impact on non-motor features and improving hardware to make it more convenient and less intrusive. In addition, a variety of other neuromodulatory approaches (e.g., various electrical or magnetic stimulation strategies) are being explored that may offer less-invasive ways to target brain activity.

In addition to neuromodulation, researchers are testing other assistive technologies to improve motor (e.g., cueing devices to improve freezing of gait) and non-motor symptoms (e.g., adapting healthy sleep patterns with light therapy). Approaches may also support the delivery of care for a more personalized, on-demand intervention (e.g., speech training applications) or optimize clinical and/or self-care management (e.g., medication adherence smartphone applications). These digital health technologies are emerging as an important part of medical care and research.

MJFF Perspectives and Role

MJFF has supported research to advance novel DBS systems and programming as well as supporting earlier clinical exploration of FUS. In addition, we have supported a range of health technologies for managing various symptoms. MJFF supports better use of technology for treatment and measurement of PD and monitors this sector to better understand the utility of these technologies, regulatory and policy challenges, and infrastructures needed to utilize these new types of therapies. Based on the intended use and associated risk of these therapies, regulatory requirements and clinical development paths can vary. Importantly, clinical adoption and utility of these technologies remains an open question, requiring more real-world data.

Examples of MJFF-Supported Neuromodulation and Technology-Enabled Programs

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Neuromodulation

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
Adaptive DBS	University Hospital Wuerzburg	Adaptive DBS	Neuromodulation	Gait & Balance	1	\$	Results pending 2027
Cortical Grid	University Health Network	Cortical grid	Neuromodulation	Gait & Balance	1	\$, Other	Results pending 2026
V-GAIT Platform	Cleveland Clinic	STN-DBS neural signatures, DBS programming	Neuromodulation	Motor Impairment	2	\$	Results pending 2025
ARC IM	Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Spinal cord stimulation	Neuromodulation	Motor Impairment	2	\$, Other	Results pending 2026

Other Technology-Enabled Therapy

Therapeutic	Sponsor	Mechanism	Approach	Intended Use ^a	Phase	MJFF Role ^b	Status ^c
TURN-IT	Oregon Health and Science University	Gait Rehabilitation	Other	Gait & Balance	1	\$, Other	Results pending 2027
Powered Wearable Devices for Walking Assistance	Skip Innovations	Mechanistic gait device	Assistive Technology	Motor Impairment	1	\$, Other	Results pending 2025
Soft Robotic Apparel	Boston University	Mechanistic gait device	Assistive Technology	Gait & Balance	1	\$, Other	Results pending 2027
Head-up Tilt During Sleep (HUTS)	Leiden University Medical Center	Autonomic dysfunction	Assistive Technology	Orthostatic Hypotension, Supine Hypertension	2	\$, Other	Results pending 2025
Soturi App	Newel Health	Digital therapeutic for medication optimization	Other	Motor Impairment, Treatment Plan Optimization	2	\$, Other	Results pending 2025
Understand Me for Life App	Teachers College, Columbia University	Speech intelligibility app	Other	Speech	2	\$, Other	Results pending 2026
ADAM+ Platform	Sibel Health	Swallowing and drooling digital therapeutic	Assistive Technology	Dysphagia, Sialorrhea	3	\$, Other	Results pending 2025

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